

PSYCHOLOGY OF THE FORMATION OF SOCIAL CONSCIOUSNESS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Ganieva Dildora Muqimovna

Teacher of the Department of preschool education,
Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7712642>

Abstract: This article reveals the forms of public consciousness. The diversity of the social and practical work of people generates a variety of forms of social consciousness. And in my article I reveal the most common forms of consciousness. Forms of social consciousness are the ways of spiritual development of reality. Each form of social consciousness has its own distinctive features.

Key words: Philosophy, consciousness, morality, religion, conscience, ethics.

Introduction

Forms of social consciousness are all possible methods of spiritual development of reality. In accordance with this, their table of contents also differs. From the abundance of various forms of social consciousness, we distinguish 6 forms: financial, environmental, legal, moral, aesthetic, religious.

The variety of types of social and practical work of people generates a variety of forms of social consciousness.

Economic concepts: - about the inner life of society (and social group, including family); - on the production and distribution of material goods; - about the ownership and management of its species; - about trade and finance, income and expenses.

Ecological is a special configuration of public consciousness reflecting the interaction of two systems of nature and society in the criteria of their joint decline. It is aimed at developing a mass strategy for preventing a biosocial environmental accident. Philosophical and methodological concepts of ecological consciousness: 1) nature is imperfect, as a result of which it is necessary to improve and improve it from the point of view of human habitation for the ideal absorption of natural nature of artificial origin. Objections: a) there is no unconditional evidence that the natural environment does not meet the best conditions for human life; b) intensive ecological creativity has the opportunity not to observe a delicate balance in nature and will make an environmental accident inevitable; c) there is a great danger that bacteria, microbes, human parasites that flexibly adapt to conditions of artificial origin, will create danger for the existence of humans as a biological species; (e) There

are still no methods for clearly predicting and evaluating the likely results of ecological production, for example, as biosocial ecosystems.

Moral understanding is a set of ideas about moral norms of human behavior, which, unlike legal laws, are supported not by the government of the country, but by the authority of the social concept and people's inner beliefs. It is based on traditions that consolidated these actions, which turned out to be necessary for the preservation and formation of individuals and society that meet their needs and interests. There are public prohibitions (taboos) designed to prevent illegal influences from the point of view of common interests. The concept of right plays a gigantic role in moral consciousness.

The strength of generally accepted moral measures lies in their legal incompleteness. Self-respect is an understanding of one's own meaning and the right to respect. Conscience is a person's moral self-awareness that evaluates his actions from the inside. Be the owner of your will and the slave of your conscience. Persons of conscience: - active (not sleeping); - catching up (repentant); - unclaimed. Morality is an ideal theoretical level of moral consciousness.

Religious understanding, along with religious rituals (cult) and religious institutions, develops a similar social image - religion. As in other forms of social consciousness, there are 2 meanings in religious: 1) religious psychology, that is, the views, ideas, feelings of the mass of believers, and 2) religious ideology, that is, a systematic presentation of religious dogmas and precepts of professional ministers and theologians. Faith is not a random branch of cultural evolution, but a naturally occurring socio-psychologically conditioned configuration of people's understanding of the world and themselves in it. Religious understanding corresponds to the impartial needs of the human spirit, and as long as these needs are not met by other forms of social consciousness, it will remain a source of ethical and aesthetic values, emotional comfort and help, the key to future loyalty.

The essence of religious consciousness lies in the ghostly doubling of the world, that is, the recognition, along with the real world, of a second, otherworldly, in which an impeccable solution to all the tragic contradictions of earthly existence will be found. There is no logical proof of the embodiment of this world; as a result, the moral and emotional act of faith is deliberately cultivated. Religion is a continuous property of human consciousness, but in the religious it is absolutized, regarded as a real spiritual mastery: a person probably feels and experiences his own involvement in the divine. The Lord of religious

consciousness, despite all the shortcomings of earthly life, is the guarantor of an irreplaceable celebration of goodness, loyalty and morality. Unbelief from the point of view of the believer is equivalent to the loss of all moral principles.

Religious understanding was formed not so much in the doctrine of the world as in the doctrine of a righteous life, that is, in the guise of a socio-ethical teaching. As a result, the belief in moral values protects their own attractiveness due to their value character and deep mental implications. The values of religion continue to attract a certain proportion (up to 10%) of the population, but this is no longer the over-reflexive religiosity of the past centuries, living at the expense of long-standing customs, but refined philosophical ideas of religious consciousness, taking into account the merits of scientific philosophy and the diversity of Eastern thought. Socio-psychological mechanisms of imitation and suggestion are also skillfully used, for example, prolonged repetition of mantras, meditation, rhythmic body movements, etc., which lead the human psyche into altered states of consciousness, "illumination".

Aesthetic consciousness is a special configuration of social consciousness expressed in the works of the world's population, in the artistic creativity of people, in peculiar emotions, experiences, impressions that arise in the process of perceiving the magnificent, sublime, catastrophic. Aesthetic understanding is usually characteristic of any act of human work, when a person considers everything from an aesthetic point of view, which actually falls within the scope of his skill and attracts these phenomena from the point of view of a specific real value. Art is the highest configuration of aesthetic consciousness, where the latter is the main goal. Art not only reflects reality, but also creates a kind of universe - a universe of artistic images.

Legal understanding is a set of legal attitudes, doctrines and emotions based on knowledge of the legal norms of society and their assessment. Unlike political consciousness, legal consciousness reflects life from the point of view of the rights and obligations of all participants in public relations. The legal understanding is normative, since it seems to regulate public relations and serves as a means of ensuring a legitimate generally accepted measure.

Conclusion

Unlike the law, which is universally binding, the provision of coercive forces to state bodies, the sense of justice is heterogeneous and more mobile, elastic. It is in the legal consciousness that the basic ideas are born, that is, informants about the configuration and appearance of legal laws. With the change in financial relations, the legal consciousness also changes, but other forms of public

consciousness also actively influence it. Legal awareness is not only the knowledge of legal phenomena, but also the attitude towards them, their assessment, which affects people's faith in the loyalty or injustice of the law or the rule of law in general.

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